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Impact of Microwave Energy, Immersion Duration and Osmotic Solution on the Physical Characteristics of Intermediate Moisture Papaya var. Red Lady

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Abstract

Papaya is highly perishable due to the higher moisture content and water activity present in it. The postharvest losses are higher because of this reason. These losses can be reduced by converting them into intermediate moisture fruits by osmosis, followed by other dehydration methods. The present study was conducted to evaluate the effect of microwave energy, immersion duration, and osmotic solution on the intermediate moisture papaya var. Red Lady is prepared by osmotic dehydration followed by vacuum drying. Papaya fruits of mature and firm ripe stage were collected, and the juice of the fruits was concentrated to 50 °brix in microwave oven at power levels 180, 300 and 450 W. Mature and firm ripe papaya fruits were sliced and immersed in the osmotic solutions for 6, 12 and 24 hrs and then dried in vacuum oven at 40 °C. The physical characteristics were determined, and results were expressed as the mean of the triplicates. The results revealed that the intermediate moisture (IM) papaya slices had the following physical attributes: moisture content (17.92 to 24.58 %), weight loss (32.07 to 47.20 %), solid gain (33.20 to 50.58 %), water loss (67.34 to 92.58 %), water activity (0.687 to 0.855), L^* (79.69 to 93.26), a^* (0.11 to 2.48), and b^* (4.54 to 10.96). The results of the study revealed the beneficial effects of using microwave energy and vacuum drying in the preparation of intermediate moisture products.

Keywords: Fruit pulp concentrate; Intermediate moisture fruit; Microwave energy; Papaya; Osmotic dehydration; Vacuum dehydration

Introduction

Papaya, which belongs to the family of *Caricaceae*, is a very important fruit crop of tropical and subtropical regions. The higher moisture content and climacteric nature of the fruit lead it to senesce quickly, reducing the postharvest life of papaya. Intermediate moisture fruits have a moisture content of 15 to 40 % and water activity of 0.65 to 0.90 (Barbosa-Cánovas et al., 2003). The lower water activity enhances the shelf life by inhibiting the growth of microorganisms (Kim et al., 2022). Hurdle technology can be employed in the preparation of intermediate moisture fruits, which include low moisture content, low water activity, and high sugar concentration (Gomez et al., 2022). Osmotic dehydration reduces the moisture content partially and helps in reducing drying time for the produce (Alabi et al., 2022; Masztalerz et al., 2021). This involves the transfer of solutes from the osmotic solution to the slices and diffuses the water into the hypertonic osmotic solution (Kaur et al., 2022). Fruit juices are gaining importance as osmotic solutions because of the bioactive

compounds present in them which helps in fortification along with shelf-life improvement (Wang et al., 2022). The intermediate moisture products developed by osmosis, followed by other drying methods, improve the sensory characteristics, viz., colour, flavour, and texture (Kaur et al., 2024). The osmotic factors that influence the mass transfer are the osmotic solution used, concentration of osmotic solution, immersion duration, fruit to osmotic agent ratio, and temperature (Manzoor et al., 2021; Özkan-Karabacak et al., 2022).

The nutrient availability in the osmotic solution directly correlates with the nutritional quality of the final product. The method used for concentration of the osmotic solution plays a critical role in the retention of the thermolabile bioactive compounds present in the osmotic solution. Microwave energy, a non-thermal energy, works by dual mechanisms, viz., ionic conduction and dipolar rotation (Potdar et al., 2022; Kumar and Gomez, 2024). These mechanisms aid in rapid heat development and help in the concentration of the osmotic solution. This reduces the exposure time to heat, thus helping in the retention of the thermolabile bioactive compounds. The microwave power and exposure time influence the retention of the nutritional quality (Chua and Leong, 2020). Drying enhances the shelf life by reducing the moisture content and water activity (Kumar et al., 2025). Vacuum drier dehydrates the produce rapidly at low temperature under low atmospheric pressure (Susilo et al., 2022), retains the nutritional compounds, taste, and natural colour of the product (Mishra et al., 2021). It aids in drying thermolabile foods. The present study evaluated the influence of microwave energy, immersion duration, and osmotic solution on the physical characteristics of intermediate moisture papaya var. Red Lady.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted in the Department of Postharvest Management, College of Agriculture, Vellanikkara, Kerala Agricultural University, Thrissur, Kerala, India. A firm ripe papaya fruit of var. Red Lady was collected from the Thrissur fruit market. Fruit juice having an initial TSS value of 15 °Brix was concentrated in a microwave oven (Samsung M1833N) (Figure I) at different power levels (180, 300, and 450 W) until it was concentrated to 50 °Brix. The time taken for the concentration of one litre of fruit juice was 3.8, 2.87, and 1.25 h at 180, 300, and 450 W, respectively. Sucrose syrup was also concentrated at the same power levels. Papaya fruit slices 8 mm thick were prepared using a fruit slicer. The slices were immersed in the osmotic solutions (sucrose syrup and fruit pulp concentrate) for 3 varied durations (6, 12, and 24h). Then, the slices were taken out and further drying was carried out in a vacuum oven (Being, Model- DZF-6032) at 40 °C and -30 mm Hg pressure (Figure II). The slices dried till the weight became constant (Figure III). The treatment details are detailed in Table I.

Table 1. Treatment details

Treatment No.	Factor 1 (Osmotic solution)	Factor 2 (Microwave power) (W)	Factor 3 (Immersion time) (h)
T ₁	Sucrose	180	6
T ₂	Sucrose	180	12
T ₃	Sucrose	180	24
T ₄	Sucrose	300	6
T ₅	Sucrose	300	12
T ₆	Sucrose	300	24
T ₇	Sucrose	450	6
T ₈	Sucrose	450	12
T ₉	Sucrose	450	24
T ₁₀	Fruit pulp concentrate	180	6
T ₁₁	Fruit pulp concentrate	180	12
T ₁₂	Fruit pulp concentrate	180	24
T ₁₃	Fruit pulp concentrate	300	6 h
T ₁₄	Fruit pulp concentrate	300	12
T ₁₅	Fruit pulp concentrate	300	24
T ₁₆	Fruit pulp concentrate	450	6
T ₁₇	Fruit pulp concentrate	450	12
T ₁₈	Fruit pulp concentrate	450	24

Moisture content

Moisture content of the IM papaya slices was calculated using an infrared moisture analyser (Hallmark Mechatronics, Model-Sartorius, MA 150C, Germany) and expressed in %.

Solid gain

Solid gain of the IM papaya slices was estimated according to Panagiotou et al. (1998).

$$\text{Solid gain (\%)} = \frac{m - m_0}{M_0} \times 100$$

(Where: m = Dry mass of the sample after chosen duration of osmotic treatment; m_0 = Dry mass of fresh sample; M_0 = Initial mass of fresh sample before osmotic treatment)

Water loss

The per cent water loss was calculated by adding per cent weight reduction and solid gain (Chavan et al., 2010).

$$\text{Water loss (\%)} = \text{weight reduction (\%)} + \text{solid gain (\%)}$$

Figure I: Concentration in Microwave

Figure II: Drying in vacuum

Figure III: Intermediate moisture papaya var. Red Lady

Weight reduction

Weight reduction of the IM papaya slices was estimated according to Feng et al. (2019).

$$\text{Weight reduction (\%)} = \frac{(M_0 - m_0) - (M_t - m_t)}{M_0} \times 100$$

(Where: M_0 = Initial mass of the sample; m_0 = Dry mass of sample before osmotic treatment; M_t = Mass of sample after osmotic treatment; m_t = Dry mass of sample after osmotic treatment)

Water activity (a_w)

A water activity meter (Aqua lab, Model: Pre 40412, Decagon Devices, USA) was used for determining water activity.

Colour values

Minolta CM-3600D spectrophotometer (Konica Minolta Sensing, Inc., Osaka, Japan) reflectance measurement was used to determine colour values with a D65 lamp as a reference source of light. The colour values L^* , a^* , and b^* were analysed using the software JAYPAK 4808 (Quality Control system, Version 1.2).

Statistical analysis

The experiment was conducted in triplicate as a factorial CRD, and the results were expressed as the mean of the triplicates. The results obtained were tested for significance with ANOVA at the level of $p \leq 0.05$.

Results and discussion

Moisture content (%)

The highest moisture content (24.58 %) was found in the slices immersed for 12 hours in fruit pulp concentrated at 450 W (T17) and the lowest (17.92 %) was in the slices immersed for 24 hours in fruit pulp concentrated at 450 W (T18) (Table II). Lower moisture content enhances the shelf life of the

product by reducing the growth of spoilage microorganisms. The lowest moisture content in the slices immersed for 24 hours in fruit pulp concentrated at 450 W might be due to increased dehydration time, which supports more movement of water into the hypertonic fruit pulp concentrate from the slices. A study by Gomez et al. (2022) reported a moisture content of 21.67 to 26.56 % in intermediate moisture pineapple slices in the var. Kew and Mauritius.

Solid gain (%)

Solid gain was observed to be the highest (50.58 %) in the slices treated with sucrose syrup concentrated at microwave power of 300 W immersed for a duration of 24 hours (T6) and the lowest solid gain (37.32 %) was in the slices immersed for 6 hours in sucrose syrup concentrated at microwave power of 180 W (T1) (Figure IV). Solid gain improves the nutritional quality, flavour, texture, and shelf life of the osmodehydrated product. The highest per cent of solid gain (50.58 %) in the slices immersed for 24 hours might be due to the increase in influx of solutes into slices because of the enhanced mass transfer characteristics. Chauhan et al. (2011) reported similar value (38.2 %) for the apple slices osmodehydrated in sucrose syrup. A study conducted by Aparna et al. (2022) in bilimbi osmo-dehydration reported similar findings that solid gain was increased with an increase in immersion duration from 60 to 180 min. Preethi and Tiroutchelvame (2013) observed similar findings for amla slices; solid gain was increased (10.28 to 13.42 %) with increased immersion time (30 to 120 min) at 50 °Brix.

Fig. 4. Effect of microwave energy, immersion duration, and osmotic solution on solid gain (%) in intermediate moisture papaya var. Red Lady

Water loss (%)

The highest water loss per cent (92.58 %) was found in slices immersed for 12 hours in sucrose syrup concentrated at microwave power of 300 W (T5) and the lowest (67.34 %) was reported in the slices immersed for 6 hours in fruit pulp concentrated using microwave power of 180 W (T10) (Figure V). Water loss is directly correlated with the shelf life of the osmodehydrated product. Higher water loss will reduce the free water available in the produce for microbial growth and prevents spoilage. Bchir et al. (2012) reported significant water loss in the initial stages of the immersion and became stable towards the end in pomegranate seeds osmodehydrated in date juice. Jain et al. (2011) reported the water loss of 28.4 % in papaya osmodehydrated at 50 °brix for 6 hours at 40 °C syrup temperature.

Fig. 5. Effect of microwave energy, immersion duration, and osmotic solution on water loss (%) in intermediate moisture

Weight reduction (%)

The highest weight reduction per cent (47.20 %) was found in slices immersed for 6 hours in fruit pulp concentrated at 450 W (T16) and the lowest (32.07 %) was reported in slices immersed for 24 hours in sucrose syrup concentrated at 450 W (T9) (Figure VI). Weight reduction improves the concentration of solids, improving flavour and texture. Giannakourou et al. (2020) reported that the firmness was increased for osmodehydrated samples, suggesting the role of weight reduction during osmo-dehydration in texture improvement. The higher weight loss in the slices immersed for 6 hours in fruit pulp concentrate might be due to the high osmotic pressure difference which in turn is due to the presence of solutes, acids, and other innate compounds. Similar observations were reported by Kowalska et al. (2023) in the osmodehydrated strawberry slices in fruit juice concentrates of cherry, strawberry and chokeberry. Valdiviezo-Seminario et al. (2024) in melon reported increased weight reduction (51.71 to 64.98 %) with an increase in immersion time from 120 to 180 minutes in samples osmodehydrated at 60 °brix.

Fig. 6. Effect of microwave energy, immersion duration, and osmotic solution on weight reduction (%) in intermediate moisture papaya var. Red Lady

Water activity (a_w)

The highest water activity (0.855) was reported in slices immersed for 6 hours in sucrose syrup prepared at 180 W (T1), and the lowest (0.687) was in slices immersed for 6 hours in fruit pulp concentrate prepared at 180 W (T10) (Figure VII). Lower water activity helps to prevent microbial growth by reducing the free water availability for their growth and multiplication. The lower water activity in the slices immersed in fruit pulp for 6h might be due to the complex nature of the hypertonic solution, due to the presence of acids, sugars, and salts, which creates a highly osmotic environment. Brochier et al. (2018) reported increased water activity (0.88 to 0.99) with increased immersion duration in the kiwifruit slices. Thatayaone et al. (2023) reported water activity values of 0.75 to 0.86 in intermediate moisture banana from different varieties.

Fig. 7. Effect of microwave energy, immersion duration, and osmotic solution on water activity (a_w) in intermediate moisture papaya var. Red Lady

Colour values (L^* , a^* , b^*)

The highest L^* value (93.26) was seen in slices immersed for 24 hours in sucrose syrup prepared at 300 W (T6), and the lowest (79.69) was in slices immersed for 24 hours in sucrose syrup prepared at 180 W (T3) (Table II). L^* value determines the lightness to darkness of the colour. Higher L^* values indicate the lightness (white), and lower values indicate darkness (black). Kumar and Yadav (2023) reported a decrease in L^* values (48.75 to 22.58) with an increase in microwave power from 20 to 80 W.

The highest a^* value (2.48) was seen in slices immersed for 6 hours in sucrose syrup concentrated at 450 W (T7), and the lowest (0.11) was in slices immersed for 6 hours in fruit pulp concentrated at 180 W (T10) (Table II). Negative value indicates greenness, and positive value indicates redness. The highest a^* value in the slices immersed for 6 hours in sucrose syrup concentrated at 450 W might be due to the pronounced colour changes because of browning, which develops a red tone, caused by higher heat input. A study by Izli et al. (2018) revealed similar findings in pineapple. The study reported increased a^* value with an increase in microwave power from 120 to 350 W (8.63 to 11.20). The highest b^* value (10.96) was observed in the slices immersed for 24 hours in fruit pulp concentrated at 300 W (T15), and the lowest (4.54) was in slices immersed for 6 hours in sucrose syrup prepared at 300 W (T4) (Table II). The negative value indicates the blueness, and the positive value indicates yellowness. The higher b^* value in the slices immersed for 24 hours in fruit pulp concentrate is attributed to the presence of a higher number of solutes in the fruit pulp concentrate and higher water loss due to the greater immersion times, resulting in colour change. Kowalska et al. (2023) observed higher b^* values (22.63) in strawberries osmodehydrated in strawberry juice concentrate compared to sucrose syrup (14.22).

Table 2. Impact of microwave energy, immersion duration, and osmotic solution on L^* , a^* , b^* in intermediate moisture papaya var. Red Lady

Treatment	Moisture content (%)	Colour values		
		L^*	a^*	b^*
T ₁	22.41 ^d	89.09 ^d	0.67 ^f	5.16 ^o
T ₂	22.73 ^{cd}	83.51 ^{hi}	0.38 ⁱ	6.11 ^m
T ₃	23.90 ^b	79.69 ^j	0.72 ^e	4.90 ^p
T ₄	20.12 ⁱ	92.50 ^b	0.25 ^k	4.54 ^q
T ₅	20.30 ^{hi}	86.85 ^e	1.45 ^c	8.57 ^j
T ₆	20.75 ^{gh}	93.82 ^a	0.45 ^h	4.63 ^q
T ₇	21.33 ^{ef}	85.65 ^f	2.48 ^a	9.74 ^d
T ₈	21.75 ^e	88.95 ^d	0.64 ^g	5.67 ⁿ
T ₉	23.05 ^c	90.39 ^c	0.32 ^j	7.11 ⁱ
T ₁₀	20.03 ⁱ	93.26 ^{ab}	0.11 ^m	7.67 ^k
T ₁₁	19.35 ^j	85.25 ^{fg}	0.15 ^l	8.32 ^j
T ₁₂	19.54 ^j	84.36 ^{gh}	0.34 ^j	9.29 ^g
T ₁₃	21.09 ^{fg}	87.19 ^e	0.46 ^h	8.75 ^h
T ₁₄	21.21 ^{fg}	87.05 ^e	0.63 ^g	9.90 ^c
T ₁₅	21.37 ^{ef}	84.34 ^{gh}	1.51 ^b	10.96 ^a
T ₁₆	22.41 ^d	82.71 ⁱ	1.44 ^c	10.63 ^b
T ₁₇	24.58 ^a	83.05 ⁱ	1.30 ^d	9.58 ^e
T ₁₈	17.92 ^k	89.88 ^{cd}	0.44 ^h	9.44 ^f
CD	0.482	1.046	0.026	0.137
SE(m)	0.168	0.365	0.009	0.048

The results were expressed as the mean of the triplicates; treatments were found to be significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Conclusion

Impact of microwave energy, immersion duration, type of osmotic solution and vacuum drying on the physical characteristics of intermediate moisture papaya var. Red Lady was analysed in the study. The study revealed significant effects of the pretreatments used viz., microwave energy, immersion duration and osmotic solution on the moisture content, weight loss, water loss, solid gain, colour values (L^* , a^* and b^*). Osmotic dehydration for 24 h in fruit pulp concentrated at 300W followed by vacuum drying at 40°C had better colour values (a^* (1.51), and b^* (10.56) of intermediate moisture papaya slices. Microwave energy for concentration of osmotic solution, and vacuum oven for further drying of osmodehydrated papaya slices, improved water loss (67.34 to 92.58 %), solid gain (33.20 to 50.58 %), and weight reduction (32.07 to 47.20 %) of intermediate moisture papaya.

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Author Contributions

KAK carried out the research and analysed the data. SG conceptualised the study and edited the manuscript. AMM, STP, PP and LPS assisted in the research and interpretation of the results.

Acknowledgements

Not applicable.

Funding

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

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Citation: Kumar KA, Gomez S, Markose AM, Panjikaran ST, Patil P and Laxmi PS (2025) Impact of Microwave Energy, Immersion Duration and Osmotic Solution on the Physical Characteristics of Intermediate Moisture Papaya var. Red Lady. Environmental Science Archives 4(1): 358-366.